

A Study on Fungal Infection in Post Pulmonary Tuberculosis**Sirigiri Venugopal Reddy¹, Ambernath Gaddale², Swetha Putta³, Mannam Saritha Samuel⁴**¹Associate Professor, Dep of Pulmonary Medicine Kurnool Medical College, Kurnool²Assistant Professor, Dep of Pulmonary Medicine Kurnool Medical College, Kurnool³Assistant Professor, Dep of Pulmonary Medicine Kurnool Medical College, Kurnool⁴Assistant Professor, Dep of Pulmonary Medicine, Kurnool Medical College, Kurnool

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: In pulmonary tuberculosis study of fungal diseases attained importance because not only prolonged use of antibiotics is required to treat this disease but also, tuberculosis leaves residual lesions which form fungal super infection. By the presence of cavities and necrotic tissue which favor colonization of fungi and whether this super infection with fungi is responsible for persistent morbidity and symptomatic state even after completion of chemotherapy. This study aims to determine the prevalence and pattern of fungal diseases in patients who completed antitubercular therapy and has sequelae of the disease particularly cavities.

AIMS: To study the various fungi that can be isolated in sputum of patients who had pulmonary tuberculosis and who had taken anti tubercular drugs.

Objectives: 1) Isolation of various fungi and its association with variables like type of disease, age, sex, presence of cavities. 2). Clinical significance of fungi thus isolated in regard to secondary mycotic disease.

Materials and Methods: This is a prospective observational study conducted from may 2023 to April 2024 at Department of pulmonary medicine, Kurnool medical college and government general hospital, Kurnool. A total of 100 patients satisfying the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included in the study.

Results: The study group consists of 100 patients among which 74(74%) are males and 26(26%) are females. Most common symptoms was cough with or without expectoration followed by wheeze, hemoptysis, SOB. Most common radiological findings were cavity (62%), followed by fibrosis and fibro-cavitary disease. Fungal isolation was more common in patients with disease duration 1 to 2(49%) years and 2-4(47%) years. More no. of cases seen within 4 years of disease duration. It is observed that in 43% of patients the interval between completion of chemotherapy and symptom onset is 1-2 years. Fungal isolation is more common in patients with diabetes mellitus than in patients without diabetes. It was observed that candida alone is isolated from 15% of cases and Aspergillus alone from 34%. No fungus isolated in 51% of cases.

Conclusion: The occurrence of fungal infections in treated pulmonary Tuberculosis cases poses a significant challenge with occurrence of dreaded symptoms like hemoptysis that can pose danger. This study helps in determining the prevalence of these infections and the most common fungal species isolated there by guiding the management.

Keywords: Fungal infections, Post PTB, Cavities, Aspergillus.

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Introduction

The study of fungal diseases has attained importance due to various factors like, recognition of worldwide distribution of many fungi, increased incidence with the use of antibiotics, steroids and immunosuppressive drugs and AIDS, development of various techniques to isolate and identify the fungus and antifungal drugs.

Each year, more than one million people who have been treated successfully for tuberculosis (TB) go on to develop a deadly fungal infection that is often left untreated because it is mistaken for a recurrence of TB. By the presence of cavities and

necrotic tissue which favor colonization of fungi and whether this super infection with fungi is responsible for persistent morbidity and symptomatic state even after completion of chemotherapy.

Laxmi Naidu et al, conducted a study, very well-established geographic variation of fungi, the study was planned since specific antifungal treatment is available; it was felt that the patients will also be benefitted by this study.

Methods

This is a prospective observational study conducted from may 2023 to April 2024 at Department of pulmonary medicine, Kurnool medical college and government general hospital, Kurnool. A total of 100 patients satisfying the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included in the study.

Demographic data of patients noted in case sheets. After thorough physical examination patients, the following investigations were done:

- 1) Routine blood investigations-CBP/LFT/RFT /RBS/Viral markers.
- 2) Chest imaging
- 3) Sputum for microscopy, gram stain, KOH mount, CBNAAT.

Patients are instructed to rinse their mouth with clean water and cough up sputum from lower airways. Early morning sputum is collected in sterile containers. A portion of it is used for acid fast bacilli and rest for direct microscopic examination with 10% KOH and for inoculation into culture media.

4) HRCT CHEST in selected cases.

Inclusion Criteria:

- 1) Patients who have completed anti TB Drugs
- 2) Patient should be sputum negative and symptomatic
- 3) Patients should have stable inactive or healed pulmonary tuberculosis lesion in chest films

Exclusion Criteria:

- 1) Pregnant and lactating women are excluded.
- 2) Patients with age below 15 years

Analysis: The data was entered into an excel spread sheet and was analysed in terms of percentages.

Results

The study group consists of 100 patients among which 74(74%) are males and 26(26%) are females. 68% are >40yrs and most common age group is 51-60 years of age. No cases seen below 20 years.

Age In Years	Female	Male	Total
21-30	5	7	12
31-40	8	12	20
41-50	6	18	24
51-60	5	26	31
61-70	2	9	11
>70	0	2	2
Total	26	74	100

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As observed from the Table below, the most common symptoms was cough with or without expectoration followed by wheeze, hemoptysis, SOB. Most of the patients had multiple symptoms.

S. N.	Symptoms	No. of Patients	%	Males	%	Female	%
1.	Cough with or without expectoration	52	52	36	69.2	16	30.7
2.	Hemoptysis	39	39	27	69.2	12	30.7
3.	Shortness of breath	25	25	21	84.0	4	16.0
4.	Chest pain	20	20	16	80.0	4	20.0
5.	Fever	20	20	14	70.0	6	30.0
6.	Wheeze	47	47	35	74.5	12	25.5

It is observed that most common comorbidity was Asthma followed by DM and COPD.

Sl.No	Comorbidity	No. of Patients	%	Male	Female
1.	Diabetes Mellitus	16	16	10	6
2.	Bronchial Asthma	24	24	16	8
3.	COPD	10	10	9	1
4.	HIV/AIDS	8	8	3	5

75 patients of 100 had positive CXR finding. Most common is cavity with 62%, followed by fibrosis and fibro-cavitary disease. Out of 62 patients with cavities 32(51.5) showed culture positive for fungi. No specific lesions seen in 25 % cases. 39(52.0%) patients of 75 with CXR findings showed culture positive.

As the table below shows, 90 patients with positive CT lesions, when compared to CXR (75%). CT was more precise in diagnosis of lesions. Most common patterns on CT were fibro-cavity and multiple cavities, followed by fibrosis. Bronchiectasis occurred in 12 patients. 10 patients showed cavity with a fungal ball.

Serial no.	Radiological pattern	No. of patients	Percentage
1	Fibrosis	16	16
2	Fibrocavitary	26	26
3	Multiple cavities	26	26
4	Cavity with fungal ball	10	10
5	Bronchiectasis	12	12
6	Normal	10	10
Total		100	100

It is observed that in 43% of patients the interval between completion of chemotherapy and symptom onset is 1-2 years. In 36% patients the onset was after 2-3 years of completion of ATT.

Serial no	Interval in years	No of patients	Percentage
1	1-2	43	43
2	2-3	36	36
3	3-4	8	8
4	>4	13	13
Total		100	100

Candida alone was isolated from 15% of cases and Aspergillus from 34%. No fungus was isolated from 51% of cases.

Sl.No	Fungus	No. of Patients	Percentage
1.	Candida	15	15
2.	Aspergillus fumigatus	26	26
3.	Aspergillus niger	8	8
4.	No growth seen	51	51
Total		100	100

It was observed that fungal isolation is more common in patients with disease duration 1 – 2 years and 2-4 years with 49% and 47.5% respectively. More no. of cases seen within 4 years of disease duration

Serial no	Duration of disease	No of patients	Fungal culture positive	percentage	Fungal culture negative	percentage
1	1-2	49	24	49%	25	51%
2	2-4	40	19	47.5%	21	52.5%
3	>4	11	6	54%	5	45.5%
Total		100	49	49%	51	51%

Discussion:

Fungal infections of lungs are important infective processes in today's practice. This study consists of 100 patients admitted to Department of pulmonary medicine, Kurnoolmedical college, Government general hospital, Kurnool. The reported prevalence of pulmonary mycoses among old cases of pulmonary tuberculosis varied from 28.3% to 59%. Prevalence of 40.7% was reported by S.K. Shome among patients of various bronchopulmonary disorders. The prevalence of 49% in the present study is higher than previous reported ones.

In present study only symptomatic (Hemoptysis, breathlessness and patients who have completed anti-tuberculous chemotherapy under RNTCP) were selected, whereas in above mentioned studies they have selected pulmonary tuberculosis cases with various durations of chemotherapy. This selective inclusion of cases may be attributed to the high

prevalence of fungal isolation when compared to other studies.

The reported prevalence of candida species in the sputum of patients suffering from pulmonary tuberculosis and other bronchopulmonary diseases varied from 8 – 80% (Norris; S.K. Shome et al; S.K. Jain et al; B.K. Khanna et al; Laxminaidu et al; Kaur et al; Chughand Chitkara; Chakravarthy et al). The prevalence of 15% in the present study is within the range. Candida albicans was the only species among candida isolates and other species were not isolated.

In the present study Aspergillus species grown from sputum of 34 patients (34%). Aspergillus fumigatus from 26 (26%) of cases, A. niger from 8 (8%) of cases. The reported prevalence of Aspergillus infection in tuberculous patients vary from 0.7% to 40%. K.L. Sobti studied only 20 cases among which 8 cases were positive for aspergillus. When compared to most other studies,

in present study aspergillus isolation rate is in par with their study.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study underscores the critical need for heightened vigilance in monitoring pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) patients even after they have completed anti-tubercular therapy (ATT). The prevalence of fungal colonization, particularly by *Aspergillus* species, among these patients highlights a significant post-treatment concern. The fact that symptoms such as persistent cough commonly appear 1 to 2 years following the completion of ATT emphasizes the potential for delayed fungal infections. This finding underscores the necessity for ongoing follow-up and assessment of pulmonary health in former TB patients to promptly identify and manage secondary fungal infections.

Furthermore, our results advocate for the integration of routine fungal screening into the post-ATT follow-up protocols. The observed delay in symptom onset suggests that clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion for fungal infections during this period. By enhancing post-treatment surveillance and incorporating fungal diagnostics into standard care practices, healthcare providers can better address this emerging issue, ultimately improving patient outcomes and mitigating the risk of complications associated with fungal colonization in the aftermath of TB treatment.

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